
GUIDELINES FOR THE SUCCESSFUL PROTECTION AND PROMOTION OF CIVIC SPACES

Deliverable 3.1

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project data: B.RIGHT PLACES
Project ID: 101142977
Call reference: CERV-2023-CHAR-LITI

Deliverable No. 3.1

Work Package: 3

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Date of submission: 30/04/2025

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Introduction

The **B.RIGHT SPACES Guidelines** are designed to serve as a **bridge** between the research findings and the participatory activities carried out with the local groups of stakeholders. As a flexible and evolving document, these guidelines bring together the insights from desk and field research and use them as the foundation for action-oriented methodologies and tools to support the development, evaluation, and protection of civic spaces in the partner territories.

The contents are organised into three different parts: the *analytical tools*, the *operational tools* and the *processes*.

- 1. The analytical tools.** In this part we present the **taxonomy of civic spaces**, which provides a categorised set of key characteristics of civic spaces, using criteria adapted from both the literature review and characteristics identified in local practices. This taxonomy, together with the resulting checklist, serves as a foundational framework for understanding and evaluating civic spaces. As part of local participatory activities, these tools can be used in a modular way to allow local groups to focus on themes, critical issues and challenges they wish to work on.
- 2. Operational tools.** In this part we present the **Toolkit**, which proposes co-design methods and tools for collaborative and participatory practical experiences. It includes methods, tools and suggestions for conducting policy workshops, which are considered as processes to ensure that the guidelines remain relevant and rooted in local contexts.
- 3. The processes.** This section distinguishes between two complementary processes: the *Policy Lab* and the *Partner Lab*.

The *Policy Lab* is designed as a participatory method to promote inclusive dialogue and joint definition of policy issues. It is implemented through interactive tools and approaches that encourage the engagement of different stakeholders and is supported by analytical tools that allow for multi-level comparisons in different local contexts.

In turn, the *Partner Lab* serves as an internal coordination mechanism among the project partners. It ensures continuous exchange, reflection and mutual learning throughout the implementation of WP3 activities. The Partner Lab supports the consistent monitoring and management of the Policy Lab process and facilitates the alignment of different local experiences.

We assume that this document will remain dynamic, incorporating the collaborative inputs and different perspectives from the project partners and the engaged stakeholders. At the end of the local activities, the guidelines will indeed be further enriched with shared methodologies, tools and practical "suggestions" for conducting policy workshops and other forms of participatory processes that bring together different stakeholders (e.g. government officials, civil society organisations, community members, academics and private sector actors) to design, test and refine innovative solutions to address public policy challenges.

The collaborative nature of the guidelines reflects the core values of the B.RIGHT SPACES project: subsidiarity, cooperation, and the co-creation of solutions that empower communities and protect democratic principles. To maximise reach and usability, the Guidelines will be disseminated as a digital document in English, ensuring accessibility for a wide audience of stakeholders.

Who are these Guidelines for?

The B.RIGHT SPACES Guidelines are intended to be used by different groups of stakeholders involved in the protection, development and sustainability of civic spaces. These include

- **CSOs, NGOs, social and solidarity economy organisations (SEOs) and other actors** who are often at the forefront of civic engagement and fundamental rights advocacy. The Guidelines will provide them with the tools and frameworks they need to overcome challenges, strengthen their initiatives and ensure that their voices are amplified in decision-making processes.
- **Public authorities**, such as local, regional and national governments, which play a crucial role in shaping the legal and institutional environment for civic spaces. By providing insights into participatory governance and inclusive policy-making, the guidelines aim to promote meaningful cooperation between public institutions and civil society.
- **Community leaders and grassroots activists** working at the local level, to whom the Guidelines will provide practical advice and examples of successful civic space initiatives, enabling them to strengthen their impact and build community resilience.
- **Academics, researchers and policy experts** committed to promoting the debate on civic spaces and participatory democracy will find in the guidelines updated material for understanding the difficulties and solutions experimented in different local contexts.

1. The analytical tools

The taxonomy of civic spaces and the related checklist are intended to serve as a starting point to guide the discussion in the Policy Labs.

The distinctive features of Civic Spaces

Civic spaces are not just physical or digital environments - they are the foundation of participatory democracy. They provide the setting in which individuals and groups can express their views, engage in dialogue, and initiate co-design processes that meaningfully contribute to social progress.

In an era of growing polarisation, democratic regression and threats to fundamental rights, the protection and expansion of civic spaces is more important than ever.

Drawing on both desk and field research, we recognise the complex and multidimensional nature of civic spaces and their intersections with different spheres - legal, institutional, political, social and technological. The original definition developed within the *B.RIGHT SPACES* framework directly builds upon the comprehensive analysis of civic spaces, informed by both desk and field research. It defines civic spaces as inclusive (physical, digital or hybrid) arenas where diverse stakeholders can engage in governance processes that shape their communities. These spaces, characterised by flexibility of form, ownership and purpose, are fundamental to fostering democratic progress, shared responsibility and collective action:

CIVIC SPACES:

- Are **places where stakeholders** can participate in **governance discussions and practices** on issues that affect their **communities**. They are the breeding ground for democratic progress, inspiring collective action and fostering a sense of shared responsibility.
- Can be designated for **specific purposes or repurposed, permanent or temporary, formal or informal, public or private**, or characterised by **shared public-private ownership**. They can also be **physical/offline, online, or hybrid spaces**. Civic Spaces can encompass diverse settings that can coexist and go from the **local to the international level**.
- Allow **all individuals**, regardless of age, background, or group affiliation, along with civil society organisations and private and public actors, to **meaningfully and collectively engage in governance practices and co-design policies**, co-implement projects and co-manage the civic space per se. This **inclusive environment** fosters political, economic, social, environmental, and cultural progress, ensuring equal access to services of general interest, freedom to choose an occupation and right to engage in work, freedom to conduct a business, and access to fair and just working conditions.
- Require an **institutional setting that respects democratic rights**, such as those addressed in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and include freedom of expression and information, freedom of assembly and association, non-discrimination, equality, the right to engage in a transparent and democratic dialogue in an open, inclusive, secure and safe environment that is free from all acts of intimidation, harassment and reprisals. Civic spaces also operate under principles of **environmental sustainability**.

Figure 1 Definition proposed by the B.RIGHT SPACE Consortium, and presented in the report "Civic spaces in the EU" (D2.1, delivered in November 2024)

Our taxonomy complements and operationalises this definition by providing a structured understanding of the conditions that enable or hinder the functioning of civic spaces. It maps the legal, political, institutional, social and technological dimensions that influence their inclusivity, accessibility and sustainability. In doing so, it reinforces the understanding of civic spaces as dynamic and context-sensitive environments that need to be supported by a robust institutional framework based on fundamental rights and democratic values. By identifying enablers, barriers and tensions across these dimensions, the taxonomy serves as a practical tool for translating the B.RIGHT SPACES vision into actionable strategies for protecting, enhancing and scaling up civic spaces at different levels and in different contexts.

The B.RIGHT SPACES taxonomy of Civic Spaces

This taxonomy provides a structured lens to analyse and address the dynamics of civic spaces, which are categorised under three primary dimensions:

- **enabling factors,**
- **barriers and threats,**
- **tensions and frictions.**

Each dimension reflects unique dynamics shaping the formation, protection, and sustainability of civic spaces in various contexts.

If we consider the articulations of the Taxonomy as modular, we have a useful tool for selecting the dimensions of local interest on which the various partners will be able to organise the contents to be proposed in the Policy Labs.

Enabling factors for Civic Spaces		
<i>These factors create a conducive environment for civic spaces to thrive, ensuring that individuals and groups can engage meaningfully in public life and decision-making processes.</i>		
Domains / categories	Descriptors	Operational challenges / Impacts on civic spaces
A) Legal and policy frameworks	Constitutional rights	Protection of freedom of expression, assembly, association, etc.
	International norms	Alignment with global standards such as the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and UN declarations
	Supportive legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pro-democratic policies and activism-friendly climates encourage the growth of civic spaces - Clear and accessible laws governing the registration and operation of SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players in the field
B) Institutional and governance support	Independent oversight bodies	Ombudspersons, National Human Rights Institutions (NHRIs), and equality bodies
	Public-Private Partnerships	Collaboration between governments, Social and solidarity economy organisations (SEOs), NGOs, CSOs and other players to support civic initiatives
	Capacity building	Learning / training (formal, informal and non formal pathways) on different topics for: civil servants, civic leaders, community groups, other players/ stakeholders
C) Socio-economic and technological enablers	Inclusive policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measures guaranteeing equal and non discriminatory access to and participation in civic spaces - Initiatives targeting underrepresented groups to promote participation
	Material support	Availability and accessibility of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding opportunities, e.g. grants, subsidies, and tax benefits for SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players - Material support, e.g. spaces let for free
	Digital enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased digital media literacy - Safe tools and spaces for online civic engagement and advocacy - Two-way online engagement between public authorities and CSOs in the policy-making process - Mechanisms to counter online hate speech and misinformation

Obstacles and threats to Civic Spaces		
<i>These challenges hinder the effective functioning of civic spaces, posing risks to freedom, safety, and inclusivity.</i>		
Domains / categories	Descriptors	Operational challenges / Impacts on civic spaces
A) Legal and policy restrictions	Restrictive laws	Complex registration processes, burdensome reporting requirements, and limits on foreign funding
	Criminalisation	Use of anti-terrorism laws to target activists and civil society actors
	Surveillance	Monitoring of civic actors' communications and activities. Political apathy, populism, and securitisation measures (e.g., surveillance) are notable impediments
B) Political and institutional barriers	Authoritarian tendencies	Governments restricting dissent and prioritising state security over civic freedoms
	Political instability	Disruptions in governance that undermine support for civic initiatives
	Resource limitations	Underfunded oversight institutions and lack of investment in civic infrastructure
C) Sociotechnological challenges	Disinformation	Online misinformation campaigns targeting activists or misleading the public
	Hate speech	Increased hostility towards marginalised groups or dissenting voices
	Exclusion	Barriers to participation for specific groups, e.g. women, elder people, youth, migrants, ethnic minorities, etc.
D) Socioeconomic obstacles	Funding opportunities	Lack of grants, subsidies, and tax benefits for SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players
	Inclusive policies	Lack of initiatives targeting underrepresented groups to promote participation
	Limited access to resources and infrastructure	Many SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players, especially those in marginalised or rural areas, face challenges accessing the necessary infrastructure

Tensions and frictions		
<i>Tensions arise from conflicting interests, priorities, and interpretations among stakeholders, legislative frameworks, and societal values.</i>		
Domains / categories	Descriptors	Operational challenges / Impacts on civic spaces
A) Legislative and policy misalignments	Contradictory laws	Conflicts between constitutional protections and restrictive secondary legislation
	Unintended consequences	Policies designed to counter terrorism inadvertently restricting legitimate civic activities
	Local vs. national priorities	Divergences in policy goals across governance levels
B) Stakeholder conflicts	Tensions between public authorities and SEOs, NGOs, and other players	Disputes over the role of civil society in policymaking
	Inter-SEOs/NGOs/CSOs competition	Rivalries for funding and influence among civic organisations
	Public perceptions	Distrust of civil society by segments of the population, fuelled by disinformation or prejudice
C) Technological and societal frictions	Digital divide	Unequal access to technology excluding certain groups from online civic spaces
	Privacy vs. transparency	Balancing the need for transparency with protecting activists' privacy
	Cultural resistance	Pushback against progressive civic initiatives due to traditional norms or values
	Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental considerations and resource preservation - Financial sustainability (the existence of civic space being linked and conditioned by the presence of supporting funding) - Leader-dependent sustainability: structures built around key individuals
	Hybrid spaces	Digital and hybrid civic spaces are emerging as crucial, though challenges like disinformation and unequal digital access persist
	Varied understanding of the scope of civic spaces	Lack of a unified interpretation of civic spaces, with multiple possible goals and aims aside from public participation (e.g. cultural participation; socio-economic community activity, knowledge transfer; etc)

The Checklist to assess our work in protecting and promoting Civic Spaces

The proposed B.RIGHT SPACES taxonomy articulates the key characteristics of civic spaces as emerged from the project's research findings. To make it usable, we have developed a checklist as a *diagnostic tool* that public authorities, civil society organisations, activists and other stakeholders can use to evaluate existing local civic spaces.

Furthermore, it can also be used as a model for designing principles to improve the inclusiveness, safety and sustainability of civic spaces.

In the development of the project activities, the Taxonomy and the checklist, used in modular form, will be the starting material to guide the work of the partners in the construction of the Policy Labs. Inside them it will be possible to define the contents on which each context will choose to organise activities of in-depth analysis and reflection, together with groups of stakeholders, with collaborative and participatory tools. The activities, organised in a procedural form, will give life to the Policy Labs and will allow us to delve deeper into some of the themes already explored in the research work, to enrich the Guidelines and to contribute to the drafting of a Manifesto which will contain the fundamental principles and conditions for good health of civic spaces.

1. ENABLING FACTORS FOR CIVIC SPACES

Focus: to evaluate the extent to which the following factors are present to support a thriving civic space.

A) Legal and policy frameworks

<input type="checkbox"/>	Constitutional rights (e.g., freedom of expression, assembly, and association) are effectively protected and upheld
<input type="checkbox"/>	Local laws align with international norms, such as the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and UN declarations
<input type="checkbox"/>	There are clear, accessible, and supportive laws for the registration and operation of SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players
<input type="checkbox"/>	There is a pro-democratic, activism-friendly climate supporting civic spaces

B) Institutional and governance support

<input type="checkbox"/>	Participatory mechanisms, such as co-programming and co-managing public policies with civil society, are actively implemented
<input type="checkbox"/>	There is support for regional cooperation networks to enhance the protection of civic spaces
<input type="checkbox"/>	There are independent oversight bodies (e.g., ombudspersons, NHRIs, equality bodies) safeguarding civic freedoms
<input type="checkbox"/>	Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) are in place to facilitate collaboration among public authorities, SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players
<input type="checkbox"/>	There are capacity-building programmes available for civil servants, civic leaders, community groups, and other stakeholders
<input type="checkbox"/>	Capacity-building initiatives and public awareness campaigns are implemented to build resilience in civic spaces
<input type="checkbox"/>	Marginalised groups are meaningfully engaged in policymaking processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Grassroots organisations are meaningfully engaged in policymaking processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	There are inclusive policies targeting underrepresented groups to promote participation
<input type="checkbox"/>	A portion of the local authority's budget has been allocated for participatory decision-making processes, such as community-led projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Regular town hall meetings are held to gather resident input on local policies and initiatives

C) Socio-economic and technological enablers

<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding opportunities (grants, subsidies, tax benefits) are readily available and accessible to SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players
<input type="checkbox"/>	Material support, e.g. spaces let for free are readily available and accessible
<input type="checkbox"/>	Digital platforms are accessible and safe for civic engagement and advocacy
<input type="checkbox"/>	Digital media literacy opportunities are available and easily accessible (e.g. learning programmes in formal and non formal settings, experiences, etc.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Diverse and adaptable mechanisms to counter online hate speech and misinformation are available and accessible
<input type="checkbox"/>	Dialogue and communication mechanisms are in place to allow two-way online engagement between public authorities and CSOs in the policy-making process
<input type="checkbox"/>	Virtual participation options are available to ensure inclusivity for those unable to attend in person
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory councils or working groups have been established to represent all local communities in local decision-making
<input type="checkbox"/>	Outreach programmes are being conducted to build trust with excluded or marginalised groups
<input type="checkbox"/>	Provisions such as transportation, childcare, or allowances are available to reduce barriers to participation for individuals facing logistical or economic challenges

2. OBSTACLES AND THREATS TO CIVIC SPACES

Focus: to identify potential barriers and assess their impact on civic spaces.

A) Legal and policy restrictions

<input type="checkbox"/>	Restrictive laws are in place, such as complex registration processes, reporting burdens, or limits on foreign funding
<input type="checkbox"/>	Civic actors are subject to surveillance or monitoring of communications and activities
<input type="checkbox"/>	Anti-terrorism laws or other measures are being used to criminalise legitimate civic activities

B) Political and institutional barriers

<input type="checkbox"/>	There are authoritarian tendencies restricting dissent or prioritising state security over civic freedoms
<input type="checkbox"/>	Political instability is disrupting governance and support for civic initiatives
<input type="checkbox"/>	Oversight institutions are underfunded, and civic infrastructure is weak

C) Socio-technological challenges

<input type="checkbox"/>	There are disinformation campaigns targeting activists or misleading the public
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hate speech is increasing hostility towards marginalised groups or dissenting voices
<input type="checkbox"/>	Specific groups (e.g., women, youth, older people, migrants, ethnic minorities, LGBTQI+, etc.) are excluded from participating in civic activities

D) Socio-economic obstacles

<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding opportunities for SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players are insufficient or overly restrictive
<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding mechanisms are complex and put bureaucratic barriers for grassroots organisations
<input type="checkbox"/>	There is a lack of multi-annual, flexible funding practices to support long-term initiatives
<input type="checkbox"/>	Thematic funding is reduced, avoiding the possibility to include areas such as activist protection, strategic litigation, and resilience training
<input type="checkbox"/>	Inclusive policies to promote participation among underrepresented groups are lacking
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players are facing limited access to infrastructure, especially in marginalised or rural areas

3. TENSIONS AND FRICTIONS IN CIVIC SPACES

Focus: to identify conflicts and misalignments affecting civic spaces.

A) Legislative and policy misalignments

<input type="checkbox"/>	There are contradictory laws (e.g., constitutional protections undermined by secondary legislation)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policies and laws tend to have unintended consequences (e.g., counter-terrorism measures restricting legitimate civic activities)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Local and national policy priorities are in conflict/ are hindering cohesive action

B) Stakeholder conflicts

<input type="checkbox"/>	There are tensions between governments and SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players, regarding the role of civil society in policymaking
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEOs, NGOs, CSOs and other players are competing for limited funding or influence, causing inter-organisational friction
<input type="checkbox"/>	Public perceptions of civil society are influenced by distrust, disinformation, or prejudice

C) Technological and societal frictions

<input type="checkbox"/>	The digital divide is excluding certain groups from participating in online civic spaces
<input type="checkbox"/>	There are tensions between the need for transparency and the need to protect activists' privacy
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cultural norms or traditional values are creating resistance to progressive civic initiatives
<input type="checkbox"/>	Environmental considerations are not integrated into the planning of civic activities and spaces
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hybrid civic spaces (digital and physical) are scarcely resilient to challenges like disinformation and unequal access
<input type="checkbox"/>	Absence of a shared and unified interpretation of what constitutes a civic space
<input type="checkbox"/>	Presence of diverse and sometimes competing goals associated with civic spaces beyond public participation (e.g., cultural engagement, socio-economic community initiatives, knowledge transfer, etc.)

4. DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR THRIVING CIVIC SPACES

Focus: to elicit some key design principles to consider to improve the effectiveness of a civic space.

The following should be in place:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Legal and policy frameworks that ensure inclusivity, accessibility, and alignment with fundamental rights
<input type="checkbox"/>	Institutional support structures that are independent, adequately funded, and inclusive
<input type="checkbox"/>	Socioeconomic support mechanisms, including accessible funding and proactive inclusion policies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Technological solutions to bridge the digital divide and protect privacy in online civic spaces
<input type="checkbox"/>	Strategies to resolve tensions, such as mediation frameworks and participatory approaches to policymaking
<input type="checkbox"/>	Investments in civic education programmes and media literacy initiatives to counter misinformation
<input type="checkbox"/>	Support for the development of transnational civic alliances and networks
<input type="checkbox"/>	Electoral processes that are transparent, inclusive, and accountable

2. Stakeholder engagement through collaborative and participatory methods: the Policy Labs in B.RIGHT SPACES

Following the identification of enabling factors, obstacles, threats, and areas of tension through the application of the taxonomy and Checklist, the *Toolkit* serves as a practical guide to collaborative and participatory methods. These tools are intended to be selected and applied based on the specific characteristics of the local context, as well as the objectives and thematic focus established for the Policy Labs.

The Toolkit is designed to support the various stages of a *Policy Lab* by offering a range of analytical, operational, and decision-making tools. Its primary aim is to foster active stakeholder participation, promote co-design processes, and encourage innovation in territorial policymaking.

Importantly, the Toolkit is intended to be both flexible and adaptable, ensuring its relevance across diverse local contexts.

POLICY LABS:

- Policy Labs are **collaborative environments** designed to stimulate **innovation in policy development**. They bring together a wide range of stakeholders - including civil servants, government officials, civil society representatives, researchers, private sector actors such as social economy organisations, and citizens - to co-design responses to complex societal challenges.
- Working at the intersection of research, policy design and governance, Policy Labs use creative and experimental methods such as brainstorming sessions, mapping exercises and rapid prototyping or pilot initiatives to generate and refine policy ideas.
- Key features of Policy Labs include:
 - *User-centric approach: Policies are developed with a focus on the needs, experiences, and feedback of the end users, namely citizens and communities.*
 - *Experimentation: Policy Labs embrace a "test-and-learn" mindset, using pilots and experiments to refine ideas before large-scale implementation.*
 - *Interdisciplinarity: By blending insights from multiple disciplines, Policy Labs address the multifaceted nature of policy challenges.*
- **Within the B.RIGHT SPACES project, the Policy Lab method is used as a framework for structuring local activities. However, its purpose is not to formulate or implement actual policies, but rather to promote inclusive dialogue, stakeholder engagement and innovative approaches to local governance challenges.**

Figure 2 A concise definition of what Policy Labs are and how this method is used and adapted in B.RIGHT SPACES

The BRIGHT SPACES Toolkit for Policy Labs

The toolkit is structured around four key phases of the Policy Lab methodology. Each phase is supported by a set of dimensions that can either facilitate or hinder the co-design process. This structure provides a comprehensive and nuanced approach to planning, implementing and evaluating participatory activities within Policy Labs.

PHASE 1: PLANNING

Objective: To define the purpose, timeline, key stakeholders and methodological approach of the Policy Lab.

Tasks, methods and tools:

- **TASK:** Record key decisions to ensure clarity and alignment in the Policy Lab setup.
- **TOOL: Register model**, a structured instrument for documenting objectives, keeping track of key stakeholders, timelines, and methodological choices.
- **TASK:** Identify and frame the core issue to be addressed within its local and thematic context.
- **METHOD: Problem definition** – a guided approach to articulating the problem, its background, and the relevant actors involved.
- **TASK:** Define clear, results-oriented goals to guide the Policy Lab process.
- **METHOD: Objective setting using the SMART framework** – ensuring objectives are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound.

Enabling dimensions for co-design:

- Clearly communicated and shared rules for working sessions.
- Transparent agendas and timeframes.
- Focused discussions centred on the agreed topic.
- Use of inclusive and accessible language.

PHASE 2: KNOWLEDGE SHARING/DISCUSSION

Objective: To share the knowledge acquired and discuss with stakeholders, comparing different experiences.

Tasks, methods and tools:

- **TASK:** Collect diverse stakeholder perspectives on the issue at hand.
- **METHOD: Focus groups** – small, facilitated discussion groups designed to capture qualitative insights and shared experiences.
- **TASK:** Generate a wide range of ideas and encourage creative thinking.
- **METHOD: Brainstorming** – structured techniques to stimulate idea generation and open exploration of possible solutions.

- **TASK:** Obtain in-depth insights from individual stakeholders.
- **METHOD: Interviews** – one-on-one conversations that provide detailed, personal viewpoints and deeper understanding.
- **TASK:** Facilitate collective exploration and collaborative problem-solving.
- **METHOD: Workshops** – interactive sessions that engage participants in analysing issues and developing strategies together.
- **TASK:** Analyse the dynamics of civic spaces and identify focus areas for intervention.
- **TOOL: The B.RIGHT SPACES Taxonomy of Civic Spaces** – a conceptual and practical framework for understanding civic space structures and conditions.
- **TASK:** Assess the current condition of civic spaces and highlight areas for improvement.
- **TOOL: The B.RIGHT SPACES Checklist** – a diagnostic instrument to evaluate enablers, barriers, and tensions within civic spaces.

Enabling dimensions for co-design:

- Skilled facilitation that ensures balanced participation and inclusive dialogue.

Dimensions that hinder co-design:

- Lack of mutual trust among participants.
- Overly large participant groups that hinder effective communication.
- Dominance of discussions by a few individuals, limiting broader engagement.
- Aggressive behaviour and lack of respect.
- Ineffective facilitation or time management of sessions.

PHASE 3: DEEPENING/CO-CREATION

Objective: To deepen collective understanding, elaborate on findings, and develop concrete proposals for action or policy direction.

Tasks, methods and tools:

- **TASK:** Map relationships, dynamics, and structures within civic spaces.
- **METHOD: Mapping workshops** – participatory sessions that visualise networks, processes and contextual factors.
- **TASK:** Explore specific themes or challenges in greater depth.
- **METHOD: Thematic working groups** – focused sub-groups addressing particular topics with targeted discussions.
- **TASK:** Encourage broad participation and cross-pollination of ideas.
- **METHOD: World Café** – a rotating dialogue method for stimulating knowledge exchange and collaborative thinking.
- **TASK:** Synthesise and communicate complex information.
- **TOOLS: Visual tools** – such as graphs, diagrams, and maps to support understanding and decision-making.

- **TASK:** Share leadership roles and encourage active contributions from all participants.
- **METHOD: Distributed leadership** – a participatory model in which responsibility is shared and leadership is collaborative.
- **TASK:** Structure and guide collaborative processes effectively.
- **METHOD: Facilitation techniques** – applied to ensure constructive dialogue and equal engagement.
- **TASK:** Base proposals on verifiable data and evidence.
- **METHOD: Evidence collection** – systematic gathering of relevant quantitative and qualitative data.
- **TASK:** Identify and assess the resources required for implementation.
- **METHOD: Resource analysis** – an evaluation of human, financial, and material needs to support feasibility planning.

Dimensions that hinder co-design in this phase:

- Rushed decision-making that undermines depth and inclusivity.
- Fatigue and low group energy, leading to disengagement.
- Intolerance towards errors or critical feedback.
- Withdrawal from discussion and poor listening behaviour.
- Reluctance to share opinions or indifference to others' contributions.
- Hidden agendas, such as self-serving motivations or attempts to influence outcomes non-transparently.

PHASE 4: ORGANISATION/REFINEMENT/EVALUATION OF RESULTS

Objective: To organise, refine and evaluate the ideas and proposals that emerged, preparing the results for sharing and dissemination.

Tasks, methods and tools:

- **TASK:** Test and validate proposed solutions with relevant actors.
- **METHOD: Test panel** – a group of experts or stakeholders invited to critically assess feasibility and impact.
- **TASK:** Highlight strengths, opportunities, and potential in the developed proposals.
- **METHOD: Appreciative workshops** – sessions focused on what works well, encouraging positive refinement.
- **TASK:** Trial proposed solutions in practice to assess real-world effectiveness.
- **METHOD: Experimentation phase** – implementation of pilot actions to evaluate results and gather feedback.
- **TASK:** Translate proposals into an actionable and structured plan.
- **METHOD: Policy planning** – the creation of an operational plan with defined goals, actions, timelines, and monitoring mechanisms.
- **TASK:** Assess long-term viability and ensure understanding of responsibilities.

- **METHOD: Sustainability assessment** – a review process to clarify roles and evaluate project endurance.
- **TASK:** Track progress and ensure accountability over time.
- **METHOD: Continuous monitoring system** – established indicators and mechanisms to measure implementation and outcomes.
- **TASK:** Summarise key findings and communicate results.
- **TOOL: Report model** – a structured template for presenting conclusions, proposals, and lessons learned.

Cross-cutting tools

The following methods and tools are applicable across all phases of the Policy Lab to support effective facilitation, inclusion, and process integrity:

- **Session governance and ground rules.** Establish clear and shared rules for all working sessions: define an agenda, set time boundaries, ensure focus on the topic, and use inclusive, accessible language to promote equal participation.
- **Conflict management.** Proactively identify and address signs of tension or disagreement through constructive dialogue, mediation strategies, and facilitation techniques that promote mutual understanding and respect.
- **Process documentation.** Ensure accurate and continuous documentation using tools such as logbooks, meeting minutes, and structured report templates. This supports transparency, institutional memory, and knowledge transfer.

Additional tools

The following optional methods and approaches can enrich the Policy Lab process depending on context, objectives, and participant dynamics:

- **Open Space Technology (OST).** A facilitation method that allows participants to self-organise around topics of shared interest, fostering spontaneous, decentralised dialogue and bottom-up innovation.
- **Future search.** A strategic planning methodology that brings diverse stakeholders together to explore shared values, build a common vision, and identify future scenarios for collective action.
- **Design Thinking.** A human-centred, iterative approach to problem-solving that encourages empathy, rapid prototyping, and creative thinking to address complex challenges.
- **SWOT analysis.** A structured analytical tool used to assess internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats, to inform strategic decision-making.
- **Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA).** A decision-support method that helps evaluate and compare multiple options based on diverse criteria, fostering balanced and transparent decision-making processes.

- **Mind mapping.** A visual technique for brainstorming and organising ideas hierarchically around a central concept, helping teams capture and structure information collaboratively.
- **Concept mapping.** A method for representing and exploring relationships among ideas, concepts or systems, supporting deeper understanding of complex topics and their interconnections.

Note on the use of tools

This integrated toolkit offers a set of initial methodological and empirical resources to guide the activities of a Policy Lab, promoting collaboration, co-design, and innovation in territorial policies.

Flexibility and adaptability are essential: the selection and application of tools should be **tailored to local contexts, specific objectives, and the characteristics of the stakeholder group involved.**

The tools, examples, and enabling dimensions provided here are not exhaustive, but rather illustrative of a broader range of possible approaches.

3. Peer learning and monitoring through collaborative exchange: the Partner Labs in B.RIGHT SPACES

The Partner Labs as a collaborative mechanism for coordination, monitoring and peer learning

Within the B.RIGHT SPACES project, the **Partner Lab** plays a central role in supporting the coordinated implementation of Policy Labs in the participating countries. While the Policy Labs focus primarily on promoting collaborative and participatory methods of stakeholder engagement in national and local contexts, the Partner Lab serves as a transnational, internal mechanism for reflection, monitoring and mutual learning among project partners. Its purpose is not only to ensure coherence in methodology and approach, but also to promote adaptive learning and peer exchange during the implementation phase.

The Partner Lab is designed as a guided and facilitated space where partners can meet at key stages of the project to discuss progress, challenges and outcomes related to their Policy Lab activities. It will support shared understanding, refine common methodologies and help consolidate national experiences into a coherent framework at European level.

Importantly, while the Policy Labs engage with external stakeholders to co-design and co-develop territorial solutions, the Partner Lab is inward looking: a structured learning environment for partners to compare practices, analyse critical choices and harmonise the use of project tools such as the Taxonomy and Checklist of Civic Spaces.

Objectives and functions of the Partner Lab

The Partner Lab has three main objectives:

1. **Monitoring Progress of specific activities.** The Partner Lab facilitates the systematic observation of the implementation of national Policy Labs, enabling the early identification of opportunities and challenges in real-time. By providing a space for structured updates, the Partner Lab ensures alignment between partners and allows for timely adjustments in approach.
2. **Facilitating peer comparison and learning.** The Partner Lab encourages open exchange among partners regarding the tools, methods, and strategies used in each national context. It supports mutual learning by exploring the rationale behind different choices and identifying transferable lessons across settings.
3. **Supporting methodological coherence.** The Partner Lab enables partners to critically reflect on the application of shared methodologies, including the use of the Civic Space Taxonomy and the Checklist, and to refine these instruments based on feedback and lived experience. This promotes a consistent yet flexible approach to implementing the Policy Labs across countries.

Structure and phases of the Partner Lab

In the implementation of B.RIGHT SPACES, the Partner Lab is to be delivered through a **series of facilitated online meetings**, or “checkpoints”, strategically placed throughout the Policy Lab implementation period. Each meeting will last approximately 1.5 hours and will centre on key themes related to the planning, execution, and evaluation of Policy Lab activities.

Checkpoint 1: JOINT PLANNING AND VALIDATION

[Proposed date in B.RIGHT SPACES implementation: Week 7-10 February 2025]

This initial meeting will focus on collectively reviewing and validating the planned management processes for each Policy Lab. Partners will present their national plans, including objectives, stakeholder mapping, timelines, and selected tools. The session will be structured to:

- Ensure mutual understanding of methodologies.
- Encourage constructive feedback on each partner’s proposed approach.
- Strengthen alignment with the project’s shared vision and instruments.

Checkpoint 2: MID-TERM EXCHANGE AND REORGANISATION

[Proposed date in B.RIGHT SPACES implementation: Week 14-19 April 2025]

At the halfway point of the Policy Lab implementation, the second Partner Lab meeting will provide a platform to discuss the **emerging dynamics, critical issues, and adaptations in progress**. This session will:

- Allow partners to report on early outcomes and engagement levels.
- Identify common obstacles and explore solutions through shared experience.
- Encourage reflection on the effectiveness of chosen tools and methods.

Partners will also begin reorganising and synthesising insights in preparation for their national reports.

Checkpoint 3: FINAL DISCUSSION AND SHARING OF RESULTS

[Proposed date in B.RIGHT SPACES implementation: Week 26–30 May 2025]

The third and final Partner Lab meeting will serve as a **consolidation point**. Partners will:

- Present the main findings and outputs of their Policy Labs.
- Share drafts or outlines of their national reports.
- Discuss how national-level learnings can inform broader project recommendations.

Methodology and tools for the Partner Lab

Each Partner Lab meeting will be facilitated using interactive and collaborative tools to enhance engagement and documentation. These may include:

- **Digital whiteboards** (e.g., Miro) for real-time visual collaboration.
- **Shared workspaces and templates** to ensure consistent data collection across partners.
- **Facilitation methods** such as open rounds, structured reflection prompts, and breakout groups to support inclusive dialogue.

The Partner Lab approach is based on the principles of **distributed leadership** and **peer accountability**. Each partner will have the opportunity to present and explain the criteria behind their methodological and strategic choices. This encourages a reflective link between the **local analysis of civic space conditions** and the **design and implementation choices** made for the Policy Lab.

Timeline overview and final outputs

The Partner Lab meetings are planned to align with the key stages of the Policy Lab timeline:

- **Policy Lab implementation period:** overall duration – 4 months [February – May 2025]
- **Partner Lab meetings:**
 - **Checkpoint 1:** Joint planning and validation (Month 1)
 - **Checkpoint 2:** Mid-term exchange and reorganisation (Month 3)
 - **Checkpoint 3:** Consolidation, final discussion and sharing of national reports (Month 4)

Following the conclusion of the Partner Lab meetings, each partner will finalise their **national report**, reflecting on the process, results, and lessons learned from their Policy Lab. These reports will be compiled into a **comparative document**, led by **Parsec Association** and **CSV Lazio**, which will be released in July 2025. This final document will offer a transnational overview of the approaches, findings, and innovations tested across the B.RIGHT SPACES project.

The Partner Lab is a crucial structural element within B.RIGHT SPACES, enabling coherence, adaptability, and collective intelligence across diverse national contexts. It reinforces the project's commitment to **methodological rigour**, **peer learning**, and **transparent exchange**, while also strengthening the capacity of partners to navigate complexity through shared reflection and collaboration. In this way, the Partner Lab not only supports the implementation of the Policy Labs but also contributes to the sustainability and transferability of the project's broader governance innovations.

Templates for documentation and reporting

Logbook template

A structured logbook can provide a chronological and concise record of activities, insights, and decisions.

Title: [Reference to the Project and to the Session name]	
1. Session details	
Date	
Time / Schedule	
Location/platform	
Name of the Facilitator(s)	
Participants	[List or number of participants]
2. Objectives	
Briefly state the goals of the session or activity	
3. Key observations/ findings	
Observation 1	[Description of a key point or insight...]
Observation 2	
More...	
4. Challenges identified	
Challenge 1	[Description]
Challenge 2	
More...	
5. Opportunities highlighted	
Opportunity 1	[Description]
Opportunity 2	
More...	
6. Results and proposals	
Result 1	[Outcome or decision]
Proposal 1	[Suggested action or strategy]
More...	

7. Next steps
[Action items with responsible persons and deadlines]
8. Supporting materials and annexes
[Attachments, charts, photos, or reference links (if any)]

Report template

Title: [Reference to the Project and to the Session name]	
Overview	
A concise overview of key findings, decisions, and proposed actions	
1. Introduction	
Brief background of the sessions	References to the participating stakeholders (organisations, institutions, individuals), how they were contacted and engaged, schedule of sessions, main topics addressed, etc.
Overview of how data were collected	References to the methods that were used to engage stakeholders, e.g., thematic working groups, mind mapping, etc (as in the Toolkit Section)
2. Main findings	
Thematic area 1	Key findings, trends, and insights...
Thematic area 2	
Other...	
3. Challenges and barriers: Summary of major challenges identified	
4. Opportunities and strengths: Summary of positive aspects or enabling factors observed	
5. Proposals and recommendations: Proposed strategies and actions categorized by priority or timeline (short-term, medium-term, long-term...)	
6. Action plan	
Plan of actions, responsibilities, deadlines	
Visual aids (Gantt charts or timelines, if applicable)	
7. Conclusion: Final remarks and next steps	
Annexes: Detailed tables, raw data, or additional documentation	